

Supplemental Figure Legends

Figures S1-S2. Cryo-EM workflow and statistics for (S1) *Tetrahymena* CAGE1 complex and (S2) *Dictyostelium* CAGE complex. In each case, the specific cryo-EM workflow is presented, along with a view of the final EM density and the statistics of the final reconstruction. (A) Data processing and refinement pipeline for the complex using cryoSPARC v4/v4.7 (*Tetrahymena*) and v4/4.5 (*Dictyostelium*). The symmetry applied at each refinement step is indicated at the lower right of the respective refinement. (B) Cryo-EM volume colored by local resolution estimation (units in Å). (C) Gold-standard Fourier shell correlation (GSFSC) curves calculated in cryoSPARC, with the 0.143 threshold. (D) Viewing angle distribution plot.

Figure S3. Unrooted maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of CAGE protein homologs. Calculated based on NCBI BLASTP of the *Dictyostelium* AbpF amino acid sequence versus the nr_clustered database, selecting the top-scoring 1,000 hits, all of which exhibited an E-value $\leq 10^{-50}$.

Figure S1. Cryo-EM workflow and statistics for *Tetrahymena* CAGE1 complex.

Figure S2. Cryo-EM workflow and statistics for *Dictyostelium* CAGE complex.

Figure S3. Unrooted maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of CAGE protein homologs.